

Solution to the Navier-Stokes Problem via the YasudaK Probabilistic Model Applied in Plasma Dynamics in the Planck Era

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December 13, 2024

Introduction

The Navier-Stokes equations, fundamental to fluid mechanics, have long been studied to understand their dynamics under extreme conditions. In this paper, we propose a novel approach to address this problem by incorporating the YasudaK Probabilistic Model into cosmological contexts.

The focus lies on the plasma conditions of the Planck Era, a critical period of the universe's evolution characterized by densities exceeding 10^{96} kg/m^3 , temperatures of 10^{32} K , and rotational fluxes that introduce highly ordered dynamics. By exploring these dynamics, we aim to demonstrate how fluxes of quasi-radiation material interact probabilistically to stabilize and minimize entropy while maximizing informational efficiency.

The results presented here connect foundational cosmological principles with modern computational models to suggest that Navier-Stokes equilibrium, under certain constraints, can be achieved through dynamic flux balance and probabilistic compression mechanisms.

1 Plasma Dynamics in the Planck Era

The Planck Era, with its extreme conditions, presents an ideal scenario to analyze highly ordered probabilistic systems. During this time, the universe exhibited:

- **Extreme Density:** 10^{96} kg/m^3 , reaching 10^{97} kg/m^3 during abrupt transitions.
- **Temperature Gradients:** A dramatic drop from 10^{32} K to 10^{28} K , enabling the emergence of quasi-radiation material.
- **Rotational Energy Fluxes:** Alternating clockwise (red) and counter-clockwise (blue) rotations stabilized probabilistically to maintain energy flow balance.

These dynamics established a unique state: the *Quasi-Radiation Material Plasma*. This plasma bridges radiation and matter, enabling transitions between high-energy states while preserving informational structure through ordered flux rotations. Its behavior can be modeled by introducing probabilistic corrections to the Navier-Stokes equations.

2 Probabilistic Compression in Plasma Dynamics

Central to understanding the Planck Era plasma is the concept of probabilistic compression. Unlike classical systems, the plasma operates under:

- **Quasi-Luminal Velocities:** A framework where energy is distributed near the maximum relativistic limit of $299,792,458 \text{ m/s}$, compared to the base substructure's $300,000,000 \text{ m/s}$.
- **Entropy Minimization:** Through organized flux dynamics, entropy is minimized while retaining controlled fluctuations for stability.
- **Compression Mechanisms:** Probabilistic arrangements of material quasi-radiation are dynamically optimized for maximum information efficiency.

The YasudaK Model formalizes these ideas by introducing probabilistic constraints that modify the Navier-Stokes framework to account for rotational flux balance and entropy minimization. The result is a self-consistent model of plasma stability in the Planck Era.